

1 **IL1R1 in inflammatory bowel disease.**

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7 Multiple SNPs localizing to the genes encoding IL1RAP1 and IL1RAP2 were isolated as disease
8 associated using CGH analysis in tumor DNA from the colons of humans with ulcerative colitis, comparing
9 tumor DNA from males versus females both with UC. IL1R1 was the single most differentially expressed
10 gene transcriptome wide, and activated, when studying total transcription in CD4+ lamina propria T cells
11 from patients with Crohn's Disease. Positions within the IL1R1 and IL1RAP2 genes are differentially
12 methylated, significant at the genome level, in the large intestines of humans with UC when compared to
13 healthy tissue. IL1R1 appears important for IBD pathogenesis in both types (CD and UC).

14 Citations

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